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Unsolved Equation: Mathematical Skills of Home Economics Students

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Abstract

Learning mathematics and developing the necessary mathematical skills is integral to our daily lives. This study aimed to determine the level of mathematical skills of the grade 11 Home Economics (HE) students in Maghaway National High School, Talisay City, Cebu, Philippines, in terms of (1) number knowledge, (2) computation, and (3) reasoning. A quantitative method engaging in a descriptive research design was utilized to gather the needed data. The Sloven's formula was employed to determine the 41 HE students as the study's respondents. The results show that the level of mathematical skills of grade 11 HE students in terms of number knowledge, computation, and reasoning were categorized as novice, which implies that HE students lack the necessary mathematical skills that play a crucial role in their academic development and future career path. To solve the existing problem the researchers concluded that the total enhancement in teaching styles, methods, and peer tutoring can significantly contribute to developing the mathematical skills of the students. This development will be beneficial in enhancing numeracy and total understanding of the use of mathematics in a wide range of concepts.

Keywords: *mathematics, computation, number knowledge, reasoning, numeracy*

Introduction

Learning the main mathematics concepts is one way to develop students' mathematical skills. According to Arbo and Delon (2022), the teaching-learning process is greatly influenced by the student's mathematical learning strategies and abilities. To fully understand the wide range of concepts of mathematics, one student must embody mathematical skills such as number knowledge, computation, and reasoning.

Mathematical skills are used to answer math problems. Number knowledge is used to understand the given number and the formula used in the problem. Computation is used to solve the problem by using the given number and the formula. Reasoning is used to understand the problem using logical thinking. If the students master mathematical skills, they can improve their problem-solving knowledge. In the study of Amalina and Vidakovich (2023), they found that underlying factors influence the students' mathematical problem-solving skills. Student's unsatisfactory performance in mathematics can significantly hinder learning and understanding of the main concepts of mathematics.

Moreover, if students cannot master mathematical skills, their academic performance will be affected. According to Nunez-Pena et al. (2013), students have low performance in mathematics because of math anxiety and negative attitudes toward the subject. Including mathematical skills is essential in developing the student's learning in mathematics. Mathematical skills play a significant role in helping students to develop problem-solving abilities. The study of Cerbito (2020) also shows that students' attitudes toward mathematics can factor into their learning and total proficiency in mathematics.

Thus, this paper determines the level of mathematical skills of grade 11 Home Economics (HE) students and how this can affect their class performance as the basis for the proposed intervention to enhance their mathematics skills and interests.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of mathematical skills of the grade 11 Home Economics (HE) students in Maghaway National High School, Talisay City, Cebu, school year 2023-2024; a basis for the proposed intervention. The following questions are the focus of this study:

1. What is the level of mathematical skills of the grade 11 HE students in terms of;
 - 1.1 number knowledge;
 - 1.2 computation; and
 - 1.3 reasoning?
2. Based on the findings, what intervention can be proposed?

Literature Review

Amalina and Vidakovich (2023) stress that the most useful cognitive tool in mathematics is the ability to solve problems, and one of education's main goals is to help students become better at solving problems. To choose the most effective teaching and learning strategies, teachers must, however, be aware of the optimal developmental stage and the variations among their students.

According to Hamapinda et al. (2021), the ability to solve difficulties is a measurement of the knowledge one has to deal with real-

world problems. This ability is essential for both conceptualization and the development of new knowledge. Therefore, determining the weak points of the students in learning mathematics can be beneficial in addressing the problems.

In the field of mathematics education, the development of students' mathematical skills has been a subject of extensive research. The development of reasoning ability is crucial to the development of all other mathematical abilities (Zaini & Retnawati, 2019). The importance of conceptual understanding and problem-solving strategies in fostering a robust mathematical foundation.

Nelson and Powell (2018), emphasize that even though the national mathematics standards place a strong emphasis on computation proficiency, students with mathematics difficulty (MD) still have trouble with computation. This implies that promoting better ways of teaching mathematics is integral to helping students struggling with the course. Moreover, utilizing various techniques in teaching mathematics can contribute to students' learning (Altakhayneh, 2022).

As the Philippines moves towards implementing the MATATAG curriculum it highlights the importance of numeracy in every student's learning. Thus, finding ways to enable every student to develop their full potential in mathematical skills is necessary.

Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative method engaging in a descriptive research design was utilized in determining the mathematical skills of grade 11 Home Economics students.

Participants

The respondents of the study are the grade 11 Home Economics students in Maghaway National High School, Talisay City, Cebu, Philippines, in the school year 2023-2024. Using Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 5 %, the determined number of respondents is 41.

Instruments

A researcher-made questionnaire was used as the primary instrument for collecting data regarding the level of mathematical skills of the grade 11 Home Economics students. The instrument was consulted by the teachers handling mathematics courses and validated by the experts to confirm its validity.

The questionnaire asks about the level of mathematical skills of the grade 11 HE students. Scores for items on each of the subscales will be summed and averaged to provide a score for each scale. This will be scaled into 5 levels Proficiency, Advance, Developing, Beginning, and Novice. A score of (1) indicates Novice, (2) Beginning, (3) Developing, (4) Advance, and (5) Proficiency.

Procedure

Through a letter of intent and sought confirmative approval from the school head of Maghaway National High School a survey questionnaire was administered. Following the instrument's distribution, the collected data were tallied, tabulated, and statistically analyzed to determine the grade 11 Home Economics student's level of mathematical skills.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensured that the confidentiality and privacy of respondents were protected by not sharing their names and identification in the selection, interpretation, and reporting of research results. The study identified and notified prospective participants of the study to minimize concerns and optimize opportunities for respondents. Both respondents were told appropriately that the data the researchers would generate would be used completely for research purposes. Respondents were informed directly and explained the purpose of the research and the data collection process. Specifically, respondents were given sufficient time to raise questions and answer any issues.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study's research question are presented in this section. A weighted mean was utilized in this study to determine the mathematical skills of the grade 11 Home Economics students.

The Level of The Mathematical Skills of Grade 11

This part is composed of three different tables, that identify the level of mathematical skills of grade 11 Home Economics students. Tables 1-3 show the level of mathematical skills of the grade 11 HE students in terms of number knowledge, computation, and reasoning.

Table 1 presents the level of mathematical skill of the grade 11 HE students in terms of number knowledge. The table reveals that the total mean of all statements is 1.97 which is an interpretation of novice. The table shows that out of 5 statements, 3 have an interpretation of novice and 2 interpretations of beginning.

The statement “I can identify the equation that has been used in the problem” has the highest mean of 2.17 with an interpretation of beginning. The statement “I can identify the needed formula in a problem” have a mean of 2.09 with an interpretation of beginning. The statements “I can identify the procedure in solving the problem” and “I can identify the operation needed in the problem” have a mean of 1.90 with an interpretation of novice. Lastly, the statement “I can identify the operation needed in the problem” is the lowest, with a mean of 1.78 with an interpretation of novice.

The table shows that grade 11 HE students have difficulties with number knowledge. Rajkumar and Hema (2019), state that several variables may lead students to competency. This implies that teachers as educators, students as learners, and the environment as an enthusiast can all have an impact.

Table 1. The level of mathematical skills of HE students in terms of number knowledge

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can identify the equation that has been used in the problem.	2.17	Beginning
I can identify the operation needed in the problem.	1.90	Novice
I can identify the operation needed in the problem.	1.78	Novice
I can identify the needed formula in a problem	2.09	Beginning
I can identify the procedure for solving problems.	1.90	Novice
Total mean	1.97	Novice

Table 2. The level of mathematical skills of HE students in terms of computation

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can solve the given equation using multiplication without a calculator.	1.82	Novice
I can solve the given equation using division without a calculator.	1.82	Novice
I can solve the given equation using PEMDAS without a calculator.	1.65	Novice
I can solve the given sign in addition and subtraction of integers.	1.80	Novice
I can solve the given equation using the trying and error method.	1.65	Novice
Total mean	1.75	Novice

Table 2 presents the level of mathematical skills of grade 11 TVL students in terms of computation. The table reveals that the total mean of all statements is a total of 1.75 with an interpretation of novice. The table shows the 5 indicators which have an interpretation of Novice.

The statements, “I can solve the given equation using multiplication without a calculator” and “I can solve the given equation using division without a calculator” got the highest mean of 1.82 with an interpretation of novice. The statement “I can solve the given sign in addition and subtraction of integers” is the second with a mean of 1.80 with an interpretation of novice. The statements “I can solve the given equation using PEMDAS without a calculator” and “I can solve the given equation using the trying and error method” have the lowest mean of 1.65 with an interpretation of novice.

The table shows that the grade 11 HE students have difficulty in terms of computation as presented also in the study of Nelson and Powell (2018), that students who have mathematics difficulties continue struggling in computation.

Table 3. The level of mathematical skills of HE students in terms of reasoning

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can solve the word problem with accurate reasoning.	1.70	Novice
I can answer the problem based on logical thinking.	1.85	Novice
I can identify the given fact on the word problem.	1.97	Novice
I can create a conclusion with the given word problem.	1.73	Novice
I can solve the word problem using critical thinking skills.	1.63	Novice
Total mean	1.78	Novice

Table 3 presents the level of mathematical skills of the grade 11 HE students in terms of reasoning. The table reveals that the total mean of all statements has a total of 1.78 with an interpretation of novice. The table shows that the 5 statements have an interpretation of novice.

The statement “I can identify the given fact on the word problem” is the highest with a mean of 1.97 with an interpretation of novice. The statement “I can answer the problem based on logical thinking” is the second with a mean of 1.85 with an interpretation of novice. The statement “I can create a conclusion with the given word problem” is the third with a mean of 1.73 with an interpretation of novice. The statement “I can solve the word problem with accurate reasoning” is the fourth with a mean of 1.70 with an interpretation of novice. Lastly, the statement “I can solve the word problem using critical thinking skills” is the lowest with a mean of 1.63 with an interpretation of novice.

The table still shows that the grade 11 HE students have difficulty in terms of reasoning. Thus, students' inability to acquire mathematical reasoning skills at the primary school level has a big influence on whether they succeed or struggle while learning mathematics at a higher level (Arshad et al., 2017).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it has proven that the mathematical skills of grade 11 Home Economics students are still categorized as novice which implies that the student's current skills need to be developed to acquire the full potential in mathematics. Also, the student's attitude towards mathematics can factor total development of numeracy. Thus, to solve the underlying problems determined, the researchers conclude the following: (1) developing teaching materials and methods that fit the interest of the students will significantly contribute to an improvement of learning mathematics, (2) conducting mathematical peer tutoring to assist the struggling students to be more engaged in mathematics will allow the students to appreciate mathematics as part of daily lives. This development will be beneficial in enhancing numeracy and total understanding of mathematics in a wide range of concepts.

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